

A REVIEW ON THE BOND BETWEEN FRP BARS AND CONCRETE

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ABSTRACT

The main parameters that can influence the bond response between FRP bars and concrete, namely the embedded length, type of fiber, bar diameter, and bar surface, were studied through the analysis of a database gathered from experimental results of direct pullout tests taken from the existing literature. In addition to analyzing the above parameters, this database also allowed for studying the bond durability in acid, alkaline, saline, and moisture environments combined with elevated temperatures for different periods of exposure. Finally, the accuracy of existing formulations in predicting the bond strength was also assessed.

KEYWORDS

Bond behavior; direct pullout test; bond strength; bond durability; environmental effects; bond strength prediction

INTRODUCTION

Reinforced concrete (RC) structures with steel bars have been widely used since the end of the 19th century. However, when RC members are exposed to highly aggressive environmental conditions or have an insufficient concrete cover thickness, the steel reinforcement can corrode, leading to RC degradation and high maintenance costs. The use of Fiber Reinforced Polymer (FRP) bars as internal reinforcement in concrete structures has become an attractive alternative to steel bars to solve this problem. In addition to being corrosion-free, FRP bars feature high longitudinal tensile strength, are lightweight, and have good fatigue behavior (D'Antino et al., 2022; FIB, 2007; Sena-Cruz et al., 2014).

Understanding the short and long-term bond behavior between FRP bars and concrete is fundamental to ensure proper behavior of FRP-reinforced concrete structures. Because of this, design codes such as ACI 440.1R-15 (2015), CSA S806-12 (2012), and Eurocode 2 (2021) have established guidelines that consider the bond mechanisms between FRP bars and concrete.

This paper aims to increase the knowledge about the bond of FRP bars to concrete through the analysis of a database developed from existing experimental results of direct pullout tests (DPT). From this survey, several parameters that can influence the bond behavior were analyzed, namely: (i) embedded length (Achillides & Pilakoutas, 2004; Refai, Ammar, et al., 2014); (ii) type of FRP (Aiello et al., 2007; Baena et al., 2009); (iii) bar diameter, \emptyset , (Achillides & Pilakoutas, 2004; Baena et al., 2009; Refai, Ammar, et al., 2014); (iv) bar surface (Achillides & Pilakoutas, 2004; Harajli & Abouniaj, 2010); (v) concrete compressive strength (Achillides & Pilakoutas, 2004; Baena et al., 2009; Lee et al., 2008); and, (vi) environmental conditioning (Altalmas et al., 2015; Davalos et al., 2008; Refai, Abed, et al., 2014).

The database gathered is initially introduced and is then followed by a series of analyses including short- and long-term bond behavior response, as well as the assessment of the accuracy of some existing analytical models in predicting the bond strength, defined here as the ratio between the maximum pullout force and the contact area between the FRP bar and concrete.

EXPERIMENTAL DATABASE

A comprehensive database of 1000 direct pullout test (DPT) results were created from the existing literature (Achillides & Pilakoutas, 2004; Aiello et al., 2007; Altalmas et al., 2015; Baena et al., 2009; Bi et al., 2011; Chaallal & Benmokrane, 1993; Davalos et al., 2008; Dong et al., 2016; Ehsani et al., 1997; Harajli & Abouniaj, 2010; Hassan et al., 2016; Kim et al., 2013; Lee et al., 2008; Refai, Abed, et al., 2014; Refai, Ammar, et al., 2014; Robert & Benmokrane, 2010; Rolland et al., 2021; Soares et al., 2020; Yan & Lin, 2017; Zhao et al., 2022; J. Zhou et al., 2011, 2012; Y. Zhou et al., 2022). This database includes detailed information about the geometry, material properties, and test results that allow the analysis of the different parameters that can influence the bond of FRP bars to concrete. Once the data collection has been concluded, test results have been excluded whenever one of the following conditions has been met: (i) specimens with missing data; (ii) specimens with smooth-surfaced FRP bars; (iii) specimens with FRP bars with longitudinal tensile strength below 100 MPa; (iv) specimens with concrete compressive strength below 20 MPa or above 100 MPa. In the end, 922 specimens were included in the final database.

Given the large number of test results collected, significant variations of some relevant properties were observed, namely: (i) FRP longitudinal modulus of elasticity – between 33 GPa and 170 GPa; (ii) FRP tensile strength – between 400 MPa and 2500 MPa; (iii) concrete compressive strength – between 24 MPa and 92 MPa; and, (iv) bond strength – between 1.4 MPa and 30 MPa. Due to the wide range of concrete classes used in the experiments collected, whenever needed, the bond strength was normalized concerning the concrete compressive strength using Eq. 1.

$$\tau_n = \frac{\tau_{\max}}{\sqrt{f_{cm}} \sqrt{1 [\text{MPa}]}} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where τ_n is the normalized bond strength in MPa, τ_{\max} is the bond strength in MPa, and f_{cm} is the mean value of the compressive strength of concrete in standard cylinders (150/300 mm) in MPa.

Outlier detection

When analyzing data, it is essential to identify unexpected values that could influence the analysis results. Data that differs significantly from the others is known as an outlier. A boxplot is a helpful tool for detecting outliers, especially for data that are not normally distributed, since it summarizes the data distribution using the median and interquartile range (IQR). The IQR is the range that contains values between 25% and 75% of the data. The limits for detection of possible outliers are represented by whiskers, which extend from the box to the maximum and minimum values within 1.5 times the IQR.

In this work, the exiting outliers were considered dependent on the type of parameter to be analyzed. Therefore, a result for a given parameter can be considered an outlier, but not for another parameter. Figure 1 identifies, per parameter analyzed, the corresponding outliers (dots in the graphs). Thus, all outliers were excluded in the subsequent analyses presented in the following sections.

BOND BEHAVIOR

Figure 2 depicts the influence of the following parameters on the bond strength between FRP bars and concrete: (a) embedded length: ranging from 2 to 20 times the FRP bar diameter ($2\emptyset$ to $20\emptyset$); (b) type of FRP: glass (GFRP), basalt (BFRP), and carbon (CFRP); (c) bar diameter: from 8 mm to 19 mm; and (d) bar surface: deformed (including ribbed and grooved) surface (DS), sand-coated (SC); and sand-coated with a deformed surface (SC + DS) . The vertical axis of each graph is the normalized bond strength.

In the following analyses, it was also verified whether or not there were significant differences between the results obtained. The Kruskal-Wallis method and Dunn's post hoc test were used for this purpose. The Kruskal-Wallis is a non-parametric technique used to detect significant differences between three or more independent groups when data distributions do not meet the assumptions of analysis of variance (ANOVA).

Figure 1: Boxplot for outlier detection

Influence of the embedded length

The database comprises DPT with 15 different embedded lengths (L_b), ranging from 2 to 20 times the FRP bar diameter ($2\varnothing$ to $20\varnothing$). The most common embedded length, representing 42% of the results analyzed, is $L_b=5\varnothing$. The use of this embedded length is explained by the fact that it is the value recommended by several guidelines and standards for the characterization of bond between FRP bars and concrete, e.g., CSA S806-12 (2012), ACI 440.3R-04 (2004), ASTM D7913/D7913M-14 (2020).

To assess the influence of the embedded length on the normalized bond strength (see Eq. 1), the embedded lengths were organized by intervals. The results for each interval are presented in Figure 2a. Further statistical analysis is provided in Table 1. Even with high values of coefficients of variation, it is possible to verify that the normalized bond strength decreases with the increase of the embedded length. The Kruskal-Wallis test confirms that there are differences between the results for each embedded length. This behavior was expected and is also observed in the case of steel bars under DPT, as indicated in (Achillides & Pilakoutas, 2004; Refai, Ammar, et al., 2014). Two phenomena can explain this behavior: (i) the nonlinear distribution of bond stresses along the embedded length, since the local bond-slip law is usually composed of an ascending branch up to the peak, followed by a descending branch; and (ii) the Poisson's ratio effect, which, due to the elongation of the bar in the

longitudinal direction, causes a reduction in its diameter (radial direction). As a result of this, there is a decrease in friction effects along the embedded length, which is not constant.

Figure 2: Influence of the studied parameters on the normalized bond strength. Note: values indicated in the graphs are the mean values and the coefficients of variation (the latter in percentage)

Table 1: Statistical summary of the normalized bond strength with respect to the embedded length

Embedded length [nØ]	NTR	Min [MPa]	Max [MPa]	Q1 [MPa]	Median [MPa]	Q3 [MPa]	Mean [MPa]	CoV [%]
2 to 4	83	1.4	5.1	2.3	2.8	3.5	2.9	28
5	230	0.4	4.4	2.0	2.5	3.1	2.5	32
6 to 7	74	0.2	3.9	1.1	2.0	2.3	1.8	49
8 to 9	78	0.7	3.0	1.8	2.2	2.5	2.1	28
10 to 14	44	0.6	2.9	1.2	1.5	2.2	1.7	37
15	14	1.3	1.9	1.5	1.6	1.7	1.6	11
16 to 19	6	0.6	1.0	0.6	0.7	0.9	0.8	22
20	15	0.7	1.2	0.9	0.9	1.1	1.0	15

Notes: NTR=N. of test results; Min=Minimum value found; Max=Maximum value found; Q1=Lower quartile; Q3=Upper quartile; CoV=Coefficient of variation

Given the clear dependency of the bond strength on the embedded length, only the test results with an embedded length of 5ϕ were considered in the following analyses.

Influence of the FRP type

Three main types of fibers composing the FRP bars were found, namely glass (GFRP), basalt (BFRP), and carbon (CFRP). Among these, GFRP represents 68% of the gathered results for the 5ϕ embedded length, being the most used due to its higher cost-effectiveness when compared to the others.

Figure 2b presents the mean values, while Table 2 presents a statistical summary of the results collected for each type of FRP. The Kruskal-Wallis test showed that there is a difference between the normalized bond strength results. Dunn's post hoc indicated a difference between the BFRP and the other FRP types, showing slightly superior results. GFRP and CFRP do not differ from each other. Additionally, it was previously shown by Nepomuceno et al. (2021) that when the axial stiffness (EA) is considered in the analysis, BFRP also presents better performances than GFRP and CFRP.

Table 2: Statistical summary of the normalized bond strength with respect to the FRP type

FRP type	NTR	Min [MPa]	Max [MPa]	Q1 [MPa]	Median [MPa]	Q3 [MPa]	Mean [MPa]	CoV [%]
GFRP	157	1.0	4.4	2.0	2.4	3.0	2.4	28
BFRP	40	1.6	4.4	2.3	2.8	3.6	3.0	26
CFRP	33	0.4	4.3	1.5	2.7	3.2	2.4	45

Notes: NTR=N. of test results; Min=Minimum value found; Max=Maximum value found; Q1=Lower quartile; Q3=Upper quartile; CoV=Coefficient of variation

Influence of the bar diameter

The diameter of the FRP bars varies between 8 and 19 mm for specimens with an embedded length of 5ϕ . The diameters were divided into intervals considering the integer value of the nominal diameter, e.g., diameters between 8 and 8.9 mm are assumed as 8 mm in diameter. The most common diameter in the database built is 12 mm, with 57% of the results. Figure 2c presents the results of the normalized bond strengths in terms of averages.

The Kruskal-Wallis test indicated at least one difference between the observed results. Because of this, Dunn's post hoc was performed. Dunn's post hoc results showed that the median results for diameters 14, 16, and 19 mm differ from the others. The 14 mm diameter presents higher results than the others; however, there are only 4 tests from one study, so they cannot be considered significant. On the other hand, the diameters of 16 and 19 mm have values slightly lower than the others, indicating that increasing the diameter can reduce the normalized bond strength.

Furthermore, analyzing the maximum values obtained (see Table 3), it is noted that FRPs with small diameters have higher normalized bond strength than those with large diameters. This behavior was previously observed in (Achillides & Pilakoutas, 2004; Refai, Ammar, et al., 2014). These authors cite that (i) the stress required to mobilize slip in small bar diameters is larger than that required for larger bar diameters; and (ii) the Poisson's effect leads to a reduction in the bar diameter due to longitudinal stress, and this reduction increases with bar size, leading to a reduction in frictional/mechanical interlocking stresses.

Table 3: Statistical summary of the normalized bond strength with respect to the bar diameter

Diameter [mm]	NTR	Min [MPa]	Max [MPa]	Q1 [MPa]	Median [MPa]	Q3 [MPa]	Mean [MPa]	CoV [%]
8	35	0.7	4.4	2.2	2.7	3.4	2.8	33
9	25	1.2	3.8	2.4	2.8	3.1	2.7	23
10	6	1.9	3.0	2.1	2.5	2.9	2.5	19
12	129	1.1	4.4	1.8	2.5	3.1	2.5	33
14	4	3.0	3.4	3.2	3.4	3.4	3.3	5
16	18	1.7	3.1	2.1	2.3	2.8	2.4	18
19	8	2.0	2.3	2.0	2.0	2.1	2.1	6

Notes: NTR=N. of test results; Min=Minimum value found; Max=Maximum value found; Q1=Lower quartile; Q3=Upper quartile; CoV=Coefficient of variation

Influence of the bar surface treatment

The stress transfer between the bar and the concrete is materialized by three main mechanisms: (i) chemical adhesion, characterized by a resistance that opposes to the separation between materials; (ii) mechanical interlocking related to the bar surface treatment that mobilizes localized forces caused by relative displacements; and (iii) frictional bond caused by shear stresses that arise from the contact between the concrete and the bar. Considering the results of a previous work (Nepomuceno et al., 2021), FRP bars with a smooth surface were not considered in this study since they yield very low bond strength values.

For this study, the FRP bars were organized into three main groups, namely (i) deformed surface (DS); (ii) sand-coated (SC); and (iii) sand-coated with a deformed surface (SC + DS). The results for each of these groups, with an embedded length equal to 5ϕ , are shown in Figure 2d and Table 4. Based on the results obtained in the Kruskal-Wallis test and Dunn's post hoc test, FRP bars with a deformed surface (DS) have a slightly higher normalized bond strength than bars with other surface treatments.

Table 4: Statistical summary of the normalized bond strength with respect to the bar surface type

Surface type	NTR	Min [MPa]	Max [MPa]	Q1 [MPa]	Median [MPa]	Q3 [MPa]	Mean [MPa]	CoV [%]
DS	88	1.1	4.3	2.3	2.9	3.3	2.8	25
SC	61	0.4	3.8	1.7	2.2	2.8	2.2	34
SC + DS	78	1.0	4.1	1.9	2.4	2.8	2.4	31

Notes: NTR=N. of test results; Min=Minimum value found; Max=Maximum value found; Q1=Lower quartile; Q3=Upper quartile; CoV=Coefficient of variation

ENVIRONMENTAL EFFECTS ON THE BOND BEHAVIOR

This work also involved the development of a database on bond durability studies. Considering the available literature, the collected data was grouped into the following types of accelerated aging tests: (i) acid solution, (ii) alkaline solution, (iii) saline solution, and (iv) water immersion. Among the conditioning environments, the exposure of the specimens to the saline environment represents half of the data collected.

Bond strength retention was evaluated for each specimen relative to its reference specimen. The mean retention was calculated for each series of tests (specimens with the same reference), and the results are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Bond strength retention as function of temperature, time, and exposure condition

Temperature effects

Typically, high temperatures are used to evaluate the durability of structures in relatively short time periods, as they favor the degradation process thus providing accelerated artificial aging. The specimens that compose the database were subjected to temperatures ranging from room temperature (20 °C to 25 °C) to 70 °C. The temperature used to evaluate the bond durability must be below the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the FRP, preventing the material physical properties from being affected. For typical FRP bars, the T_g varies between 93 °C and 120 °C (ACI 440.1R-15, 2015). According to Ascione et al. (2016), T_g should be at least 20 °C higher than the maximum temperature in the accelerated artificial aging tests. In this work, only studies complying with these values were considered.

From the database, it is possible to observe a wide variation in the values of the bond strength retention, with a minimum of 63% at 60 °C (acid solution) and a maximum of 173% at 40 °C (saline solution). Figure 3a shows that the collected data is concentrated in two main temperatures, room temperature, and 60 °C. These are also the only temperatures with results for all the considered conditions.

The Kruskal-Wallis test did not indicate a significant difference in bond strength retention results with increasing temperature for acid and water immersion exposure. In the alkaline environment, the bond strength retention at 50 °C differed from others and was slightly higher. Considering the exposure to the saline environment, it was found that the results obtained at room temperature and 40 °C were similar and superior to those obtained at other temperatures. Approximately 1/3 of the results show

retentions higher than one, i.e., aged specimens showed higher strength than corresponding unaged (reference) specimens. This result may be explained by the improved concrete properties over time.

Time effects

Time is a crucial parameter to take into account while discussing durability. The data collected allowed the evaluation of specimens conditioned up to a maximum of 240 days of exposure. Figure 3b shows that most of the data available (83% of the tests) is for conditioning times between 30 and 90 days (720 h to 2160 h). The database minimum and maximum bond strength retention values were given at 75 days (62% of bond strength retention) and 240 days (144% of bond strength retention), respectively.

As before, the Kruskal-Wallis test indicated that the bond strength retention results for acid and water environments did not differ significantly with increasing exposure time. For the alkaline environment, the Kruskal-Wallis test showed that the values differ. These results showed a slight increase in bond strength retention with increasing exposure time. On the other hand, a downward trend was observed with increasing time for specimens conditioned in the saline environment. Half of the results with retentions above 100% are in the alkaline environment.

BOND STRENGTH PREDICTION

In this work, the accuracy of existing formulations to predict the bond strength was also assessed. Therefore, the provisions of ACI 440.1R-15, CSA S806-12 and Eurocode 2 were analyzed. Only specimens with embedded length equal to $5\emptyset$ were considered in this study.

ACI 440.1R-15

The equation specified by the American Concrete Institute (ACI 440.1R-15, 2015) is based on a database of 269 beam bond tests that considered various types of FRP (the most common being GFRP), bar surfaces, diameters, and failure modes of the tests. A linear regression of the normalized bond strength ($\tau_{\max}/\sqrt{f_{ck}}$) versus the normalized concrete cover (c/\emptyset) and diameter (\emptyset/l_b) resulted in the following bond strength relationship:

$$\frac{\tau_{\max}}{0.083\sqrt{f_{ck}}} = 4.0 + 0.3 \frac{c}{\emptyset} + 100 \frac{\emptyset}{l_b} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

where c is the concrete cover, which is equal to the minimum of (i) the cover to the center of the bar and (ii) one-half of the center-on-center spacing of the bars considered.

CSA S806-12

For FRP bars in tension, the Canadian Standards Association (CSA S806-12, 2012) provides the following equation to determine the development length:

$$l_b = 1.15 \frac{k_1 k_2 k_3 k_4 k_5}{c} \frac{\sigma_f}{\sqrt{f_{ck}}} A_b \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

where c is the concrete cover, which should be the smaller of (i) the cover to the center of the bar and (ii) two-thirds the center-on-center spacing of the bars considered; A_b is the area of an individual bar; σ_f is the tensile stress on the FRP bar; and k_n are modification factors, which must be taken as follows: k_1 is the bar location factor (1.3 for horizontal reinforcement placed more than 300 mm of fresh concrete is cast below the bar, 1.0 for other cases); k_2 is the concrete density factor (1.3 for low density, 1.2 for semi-low density, 1.0 for normal density); k_3 is the bar size factor (0.8 for $A_b \leq 300$ mm², 1.0 for $A_b > 300$ mm²); k_4 is the fiber factor (1.0 for CFRP and GFRP, 1.25 for AFRP); and k_5 is the bar surface factor (1.0 for surface roughened or sand coated or braided surfaces, 1.05 for spiral pattern or ribbed surfaces, 1.8 for indented surfaces). As the standard does not consider BFRP bars, the modification factor k_4 was considered equal to 1.0 when BFRP was used.

Eq. 3 can be rewritten in terms of tensile stress and substituted in the equilibrium equation of an FRP bar embedded in concrete (Eq. 4), thus allowing for determining the bond strength as shown in Eq. 5.

$$\tau_{\max} \pi \emptyset l_b = \sigma_f A_b \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

$$\tau_{\max} = \frac{c \sqrt{f_{ck}}}{1.15(k_1 k_2 k_3 k_4 k_5) \pi \emptyset} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

Eurocode 2 (Pre-standard)

The draft version of the new Eurocode 2 (EN 1992-1-1, 2021), prEN 1992-1-1:2021, presents its equation (Eq. 6) for directly calculating the anchorage length. The Eurocode 2 imposes a minimum anchorage length of $10\emptyset$. However, in this, study the proposed formulation was also assessed to understand its accuracy for lower anchorage lengths, namely an anchorage length of $5\emptyset$, which is that recommended by several guidelines and standards for the characterization of bond between FRP bars and concrete (see section Influence of the embedded length).

$$l_b = k_{lb} k_{cp} \emptyset \left(\frac{\sigma_f}{217} \right)^{\eta_\sigma} \left(\frac{25}{f_{ck}^*} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{\emptyset}{20} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\frac{1.5\emptyset}{c} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \geq 10\emptyset \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

$$f_{ck}^* = \left(\frac{f_{bd,100a}}{0.315} \right)^{1.5} \leq 1.1 f_{ck} \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

$$l_b \geq \left(\frac{\emptyset}{4} \right) \left(\frac{\sigma_f}{f_{bd,100a}} \right) \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

where concrete cover (c) must be the minimum of (i) the cover to the bar and (ii) one-half of the bars being developed; k_{cp} is the coefficient for casting effects (1.0 for good bond conditions, 1.2 for poor bond conditions, 1.4 for all bars executed under bentonite or similar slurries); k_{lb} is the coefficient for the load (50 for persistent and transient design situations, 39 for accidental design situations); η_σ is the coefficient for the tensile stress of the bar (1.0 for $\sigma_f \leq 217$ MPa, 1.5 for $\sigma_f > 217$ MPa); and $f_{bd,100a}$ is the long-term bond strength of the bar.

As the results in the database were taken in instantaneous quasi-static tests and f_{ck}^* considers the long-term bond behavior, f_{ck}^* will be taken equal to f_{ck} in this work. Eq. 8 considers long-term behavior and aims at preventing long-term failure.

Eq. 6 can be rewritten in order to determine the bond strength, as shown in the following equation:

$$\tau_{\max} = \frac{54.25\emptyset}{l_b} \left[\left(\frac{l_b}{k_{lb} k_{cp} \emptyset} \right) \left(\frac{f_{ck}}{25} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{20}{\emptyset} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\frac{c}{1.5\emptyset} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right]^{\frac{1}{\eta_\sigma}} \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

Comparisons between the design specifications

Among the various parameters considered in the equations presented above, all the standards indicate that the bond strength increases with the increase in the concrete compressive strength by a certain proportionality. Figure 4 confirms, even with the high dispersion of the results, the tendency for the bond strength to increase at a certain proportionality of $\sqrt{f_{ck}}$ (see best fitting lines in Figure 4). In addition to the concrete compressive strength, the guidelines have other common factors that affect the bond strength, such as the bar diameter, concrete cover, and bar location.

Figure 5 presents the results obtained from the equations proposed by the design models for the bond strength of FRP to concrete. Figure 5 is divided into two parts. On the left, the calculated bond strength is plotted against the experimental data for the three formulations considered. For optimal prediction, the data points must coincide with the dashed line. Then, on the right, the boxplot of the $\tau_{\text{exp}}/\tau_{\text{cal}}$ is shown, where the safety suitability, used before in (Mohammadi et al., 2023), of the calculated results is also indicated.

Figure 4: Bond strength vs. concrete compressive strength $\sqrt{f_{ck}}$

Figure 5: Calculated vs. experimental bond strength (left) and boxplot of τ_{exp}/τ_{cal} (right)

Analysis of Figure 5 reveals that the bond strength results obtained experimentally are generally higher than those calculated according to the design specifications. Conservative or extremely conservative results are observed, namely 48% in ACI 440.1R, 35% in CSA S806, and 96% in Eurocode 2. Regarding appropriate safety, they are 35% in ACI 440.1R, 38% in CSA S806, and only 2% in Eurocode 2, as shown in Table 5. In addition to assessing the safety suitability of the models, two types of error metrics were calculated to evaluate their accuracy, namely the mean absolute error (MAE) and the root mean squared error (RMSE), also presented in Figure 5. Considering the adequacy of the results for safety and the error metrics obtained, the bond strength predicted by the ACI 440.1R is the closest to the experimental results that compose the database.

Table 5: Suitability of results to the safety

Model	Extremely conservative	Conservative	Appropriate safety	Non-conservative	Extremely non-conservative
ACI 440.1R-15	3%	45%	35%	15%	2%
CSA S806-12	5%	30%	38%	21%	6%
Eurocode 2	82%	14%	2%	1%	1%

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the short-term behavior and durability of the bond between FRP and concrete were evaluated by investigating the main parameters that may influence the bond strength. Furthermore, the performance of different models, namely ACI 440.1R, CSA S806, and Eurocode 2, to predict bond strength was also analyzed. Based on the main results and discussion presented, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- i. Due to the Poisson's ratio effect and the nonlinear distribution of the shear stresses along the embedded length, as the embedded length increased, a decrease in the normalized bond strength was observed, as expected;
- ii. For a fixed value of the embedded length, i.e., $L_b = 5\phi$, the types of FRP and surface seem to have a minor influence on the normalized bond strength. BFRP and deformed surfaces provided the highest results;
- iii. When the embedded length was fixed, i.e., $L_b = 5\phi$, a decreasing trend in normalized bond strength was observed with increasing bar diameter;
- iv. When analyzing the bond durability of FRP to concrete, it is concluded that the effect of temperature and exposure times for the conditions in acid and water environments did not produce significant changes in the bond strength. In the alkaline environment, an increase in bond strength retention was observed over time, while saline exposure generated a decrease in bond strength retention;
- v. Among the models presented, the ACI 440.1R-15 is the most suitable for the experimental data considered, having presented the lowest error values and the best suitability for safety.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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